

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Mamirjonova Mohichehrabonu Ulug'bek qizi

O'ZBEK VA KOREYS XALQ OG'ZAKI IJODIDA AYOL TIMSOLINING AHAMIYATI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/APREL

